

A Validation Study of Automated Analysis of Noun Phrase Complexity

Ichika Yamaguchi (Tokyo University of Foreign Studies, Japan)

Automated tools for writing developmental measurements are increasingly used for analyzing various types of learners' production in recent years, even though these tools were originally developed and validated for texts produced by advanced learners. The specific characteristics found in the text produced by less advanced learners, such as grammatical errors and improper punctuation usage, could potentially affect the accuracy and reliability of these automated tools. This study aims to examine the reliability of indices of noun phrase complexity computed in TAASSC, Tool for the Automatic Analysis of Syntactic Sophistication and Complexity (Kyle, 2016) for L2 English produced by learners ranging from A1 to B2 level on the CEFR scale. To this end, manual and automated analyses of 100 texts from the EF-Cambridge Open Language Database (EFCAMDAT) (Geertzen et al., 2013) are compared. The target indices include measurements of adjectival modifiers per nominal, prepositions per nominal, verbal modifiers per nominal and relative clause modifiers per nominal. Based on the quantitative comparison, this study demonstrates how the accuracy of automated analysis of noun phrase complexity is affected by the proficiency levels of the learners. Furthermore, through both the quantitative and qualitative analyses, this study identifies which specific features found in learners' text are causing a decrease in accuracy. Based on the results, it is further discussed how to improve the accuracy of automatic computation of indices through the pre-processing steps prior to automated analyses, in which raw data are cleaned and transformed into a way that is suitable for further analysis. The findings of this study will inform future research that seeks to identify criterial features for distinguishing learners of different proficiency levels based on the characteristics of noun modification.